

PROVERBS AND THEIR SIGNIFICANCE IN THE EDUCATIONAL PROCESS

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Abstract: Proverbs can be called an encyclopedia of life, a folk encyclopedia, a unique artistic and historical chronicle. They sharpen people's minds, make their speech clear and impressive, teach them to choose the right path in life, to solve life's puzzles and problems correctly. Also, proverbs are very ancient as the smallest examples of oral creativity that summarize the worldview, cultural, household life, and thought treasure of the people who created them.

Key words: education, proverb, heritage, paremic unity, pedagogy

Main part:

The theme of proverbs created by mankind is wide and varied. In particular, proverbs have been famous since ancient times for their poetry and didacticism, thematically so rich, so wide, so diverse that they contain everything from the most complex problems of social life to the smallest customs of family life, and high moral values. from the flaws to the small flaws in the character of people, from the philosophical outlook to the characteristics of the smallest animals. In short, there is no sphere of nature and social life that is not reflected in proverbs. Proverbs, in turn, serve as the most necessary and time-tested reliable source in the field of pedagogy, that is, in the process of education and training. Of course, it would be appropriate if we use them effectively and appropriately.

In the process of mutual communication, we often use folk proverbs to prove our point. This helps us to make our speech beautiful, attractive and reliable. For

example, there is such an opinion about raising a child: "You should not raise your child, first of all raise yourself." No matter how much you tell your child not to do something wrong, if you do the same thing yourself, your child will repeat the same thing just like you. A child is a mirror."

Studying the proverbs, proverbs and sayings that have been living as an inseparable part of the rich spiritual heritage of our people, showing the people's life and human feelings reflected in them has always become relevant. As we know, folklore includes epics, legends, proverbs and sayings. Proverbs are particularly important as examples of folk art that show the spiritual image and identity of the Uzbek nation. Studying and teaching proverbs instills respect for one's nation in the spirituality of our youth and pride in their hearts. We can consider folklore as one of the sources of the way of life of our people. Proverbs are a great example of folk art. Learning proverbs will greatly help us to develop respect for our language, to instill it in the minds of our young people and to develop a sense of pride in our values. At the same time, comparing our proverbs with foreign proverbs and studying them will give us a great incentive to respect other nations and to be aware of their world view.

It is known that education is given more in the educational process. From the day children come to school, a desire to learn is formed. They gradually develop a need for knowledge, and through this, students begin to receive spiritual nourishment. With this, high feelings such as yearning for the future, desire, thirst for work, honesty in charity, love for the motherland, selflessness, national pride, perseverance, kindness, friendship, and goodness appear in the child. Of course, the role of folk proverbs in this process is incomparable. In particular, works in the genre of proverbs also help to eliminate vices such as rudeness, blindness, lying, laziness, carelessness in children.

Summary:

Folk proverbs have been refined over the centuries, have acquired a classic

appearance and meaning, and as a paremic unit actively participating in speech, they are the interpretation and description of people's values, customs and traditions, history and culture, education and upbringing, etiquette issues, in general, it is a multifaceted phenomenon that fully demonstrates the mentality of the nation. The subject range of proverbs created by folklore is wide and varied. In particular, proverbs have been famous since ancient times for their poetry and didacticism, thematically so rich, so wide, so diverse that they contain everything from the most complex problems of social life to the smallest customs of family life, and high moral values. from the flaws to the small flaws in the character of people, from the philosophical outlook to the characteristics of the smallest animals. In short, there is no sphere of nature and social life that is not reflected in proverbs. Proverbs, in turn, serve as the most necessary, time-tested reliable source in the field of pedagogy, that is, in the process of education and training. Proverbs are divided into more than seventy topic groups in collections. Among them, those related to the issue of speech culture, behavior, communication etiquette, in the internal classification, speaking little, listening, keeping silent, sweet talk, correct speech, observation, Homeland, profession, child upbringing and includes many topics. Of course, it would be appropriate if we use them effectively and appropriately.

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